
Library Services and Facilities for the Persons with Disability Users in University Libraries in Paschim Medinipur District, West Bengal

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on the library services provide by the University Libraries for Persons with disability users. In the current digital age, information and communication technology is crucial to provide library users improved services. This essay attempts to paint a picture of the software and Information technologies that are helpful in offering services to persons with disabilities. This essay highlights the University Libraries advantages and disadvantages. University Libraries provide services to individuals with a range of disabilities, including low vision, blindness, hearing loss, and mobility

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Introduction:

Everyone needs education, which has been acknowledged as the primary transforming force capable of physically rescuing generations from the grip of poverty and obstacles to growth and development. Education has a formative effect on thinking, creation, skill, efficiency and physical ability of an individual. University libraries arose worldwide along with growth in education, publications and literacy. University libraries have always been a focal point of human life.

It is a useful tool that allows everyone to have access to the archives of human ideas, thoughts, and creative imagination. It is concerned with reviving people's spirits by providing literature for leisure and enjoyment as well as the delivery of advanced technological, scientific, and sociological knowledge.

From a library standpoint, "services" refers to the materials, events and initiatives etc. that libraries offer to help patrons satisfy their information needs. Information agencies and libraries were among the institutions aiming to become establishing appropriate information retrieval methods and creating accessible, accommodating spaces for their Persons with disabilities. The main service provides by a library are; Lending services, Reading room services, Reference service including Reader Guidance, Literature Search, Ready Reference services, Current Awareness Service and Selective Dissemination of Information etc. The services included Newspaper clipping service, Abstracting and Indexing Services, Document Delivery Services, Digital Library Services, Internet Services, Facsimile Services including Xerox, Print Scanning of documents etc.

Definition: Disability, according to the United Nations is a general term that can be divided into two categories. Disability is “long-term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory impairments which in interaction with the various attitudinal and environmental barriers, hinders full and effective participation in a society”.

"Differently abled" is a euphemism term for someone who may have previously been labelled as disabled, handicapped, challenged, or having special needs. It may have an impact on people who have mostly mental or physical disability.

In certain circles, the descriptor is seen as more politically correct since it acknowledges that, in contrast to the stereotype created by the terms disabled or handicapped, persons with physical and mental disabilities nonetheless possess disabilities.

Type of Disability:

Persons with Disabilities: According to CEPD (2006), A/RES/61 106, the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and its Optional Protocol, “Persons with disabilities to include those who have long-term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory impairments which in interaction with various barriers may hinder their full and effective participation in society on an equal basis with others.”

Physical Disability: Physical disabilities are defined as limitations in an individual's physical functioning, mobility, dexterity, or endurance. Other physical disabilities include conditions like blindness, epilepsy, respiratory diseases, and sleep disorders that impede other aspects of everyday life.

Sensory disabilities: When one of your senses—sight, hearing, smell, or touch—is impaired, it is called sensory impairment. Special awareness and taste are no longer considered typical sensory disability classifications.

Vision impairment: A complete or almost complete lack of perception is implied by blindness. Although they will rely more on information from other sources, a person with limited vision may still be able to use some aspects of visual perception.

Hearing impairment: Either all or a portion of the auditory spectrum may be affected by this disorder. Individuals who have a significant hearing loss are called "deaf," but those who have a slight or moderate hearing loss are called "hard-of-hearing."

Divyangjan: "Divine body" is what the word "Divyang" signifies. Following his ascent to power, Prime Minister Narendra Modi popularized it and proposed that the term be applied to individuals with disabilities, who are otherwise referred to as "Viklang" in the local dialect.

Figure 1. Type of Disability

Assistive Technology and Services:

Assistive Services for Blind Users: The following assistive services can be offered to users with visually disability:

- *Software for JAWS Pro Talking:* By transforming a standard PC into a talking PC with the Jaws Pro Talking program, visually impaired people can use computers and the Internet on their own. Additionally, the software teaches visually handicapped people how to use computers.
- *Software for reading Kurzweil 1000 OCR:* Without the assistance of a volunteer reader, the program offers blind persons exceptional assistance in reading any printed book from the library. The software is utilized in conjunction with a PC and scanner.
- *Software for Magic Magnification Pro:* Users with limited vision can watch the monitor screen and use the add-on support tools to improve visibility thanks to the software's ability to enlarge the screen from 2x to 16x.
- *Talking Typing Instructor Pro:* Talking Typing Teacher Pro was created specifically to help blind people learn how to use a keyboard and increase their typing speed in a methodical way. Complete instructions and practice exercises are included with the software. Even those with low vision may read and learn to type thanks to the program's comprehensive display of all courses.
- *Braille Scanning Software – OBR (Optical Braille Recognition):* With a standard A4 scanner, users may read single- and double-sided Braille texts thanks to a Windows application called Optical Braille Recognition (OBR). It scans the Braille document, analyzes its dot pattern, and then transforms it into standard text that can be seen on a computer screen.

Assistive Services for Deaf & Dumb: People with speech and hearing impairments can receive the following assistive services.

- Displaying films or information in sign language.
- Information via text telephones and/or email.
- Text that is easy to read and contains information.
- For users who were born deaf or who became deaf before learning to speak, the material is easy to read.
- **Services to Help People Who Struggle with Reading:** Users with reading disabilities may be eligible for the following assistive services.

- Text that is easy to read and contains information.
- Data in DAISY format, CD/DVD, or audio/video tape.
- Data obtained via the library's website.
- **Assistive Services for Physical Disabilities:** Users with physical disabilities can receive the following assistive services.
 - Data in DAISY format, CD/DVD, or audio/video tape.
 - Data obtained via the library's website.
- **Assistive Services for Cognitively Disabled People:** Users who have cognitively disabled people can benefit from the following assistive services:
 - Text that is easy to read and contains information.
 - Data in DAISY format, CD/DVD, or audio/video tape
 - Data obtained via the library's website.

Objectives of the study:

- To ascertain whether university libraries in Paschim Medinipur provide information and library services to people with disabilities.
- To identify the physical environment, infrastructural requirements of disabled users in University Libraries in Paschim Medinipur.
- To determine what kind of equipment is being given to impaired users so they can access the necessary resources (Internet, CD-ROMs, books, etc.)
- Present the University Libraries' collection to people with disabilities in order to examine it.
- To analyze and evaluate the present status, activities and Government facilities for different able users.

Review of literature: Kinnell, Margaret, Yu, Liangzhi and Creaser, Claire (2000) are based on the wide access of Visually Impaired users in UK. It also aims to provide how best services could be provided to the visually impaired people and political decision makers and managers of public library would be fully informed. This paper gives a detailed study on the social environment and visually impaired people the impact public libraries and information and communication technologies on the said users. UK Public

libraries best serve to the visually impaired people 1970-1997. UK public library services to visually impaired people.

Hernon, Peter and Philip Calvert (2006) Hernon and Calvert, and their colleagues investigate deep into the library services and the quality of services for students with disabilities. He emphasizes that single chapter will not be adequate for discussion but I must be discussed in various chapters. This discussion will be relevant for library instructors to acquire relevant information and materials and it would be helpful in students with disabilities.

Koulikourdi (2008) highlighted the use of assistive technologies (AT) in Greek libraries, unveiled the relationship between AT suppliers and library authorities and achieved a better understanding from companies' and libraries' perspective

R.I Echezona, N. Osadebe and B.E Asogwa (2011) points out that physically challenged persons should be come into main stream and libraries really have some challenges to provide information to the physically challenged persons. So, libraries shall have to adopt different strategies for them. If it is not possible to us to put them into the main stream of society them every talk will be a tall talk. This study emanated that every person has right to access to the library. They will be given information under different format and be able to use to know their opinion and grow interest in participation.

Roy (2011) investigated that undergraduate student have great interest to set information while surveying undergraduate college of the Jalpaiguri district. Students get their fulfilment from resources availability, services accessibility provided by libraries maximum numbers of student are depends on libraries but because of well-furnished facilities students wasted its real benefits. However, the result is all satisfactory.

Ekwelem (2013) discussed about the library services to disabled persons in digital era: the research work was done to point out the use of different electronic resources by persons of disability and some users of universities in South-East Nigeria. Users with visual impairments can access electronic resources such as online public access catalogues and taped books. Other colleges that cater to people with disabilities do not offer the following: assistive devices, alternate formats, personal support, transportation services, adapted furniture, building modifications, low-tech equipment, environmental adaptations, etc. There needs a large sum of money to buy all the above mentioned equipments and it is sometimes mentioned as constraints. An ideal library shall be a library where universal accessibility and usability is facilitated.

Hombal (2016) highlights Human rights and empowerment of differently abled persons. For this reasons library should be designed the role of challenged friendly librarians. The study highlights copyright challenges, role of inclusive libraries. All the discussion takes instances from Mysore University library.

Khan (2016) conducted a comparative analogy with the extent of use Grey Literature by the Visually Challenged members of the library Mysore city. The study highlights use of assistive technology. Papers are certainly on obstracle for differently abled users.

Venkatesha (2016) this study highlights the use of various assistive technologies by physically challenged people. Question is put like that to what extent the physically challenged persons are familiar with the technology used for accessing and reading. This article explains that today libraries and university libraries use various hardware and software for reading and research training is a must to use different tools equipment effectively.

Udaya Kiran K. (2016) stresses electronic information resources available on the web sites and how it would best serve visually challenged people; student and faculty members should access books available on journal. They should use assistive technology for the self-reliance.

Yetunde Lola Akolade, Adeyinka Tell, Hawwa Bolanle Akanbi – Ademolake and Mulikat Yetunde Adisa (2016) discusses physically challenged people need some information as the people without disability. Libraries are organizations to provide information to all irrespective of considering social status or physically abnormalities. Those persons who are more prone to studies, library is liable to provide information.

Onsinyo Charity Nyaboke (2018) discusses persons with disabilities are not benefited from the library and information services. The researcher adopted descriptive survey design and pointed out certain look in the following matters staff incapacity, structural incapacibilities absence of special libraries and information services. He also raises the questions towards the national and international policy framework. If national policy framework could be amended it would be helpful for the persons with disability persons.

Scope of the Study: Covers only the users who are differently abled in University Libraries in Paschim Medinipur. Considered disabilities as define in the Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation.

Methodology: The two methods indicated below were used to collect data. sources for documentaries such as books, journal papers, government materials, the Internet, etc. Data collected through a questionnaire at university libraries.

Data Collection: According to published research, Paschim Medinipur University Libraries offer unique services to patrons with disabilities. This study was carried out using the four libraries in Paschim Medinipur Municipal area situated in the state of West Bengal.

Data Analysis: As stated in the questionnaire, the data was received, examined, and presented under the four-heading listed below.

- Physical entry to the library's resources and grounds
- Access to library materials
- Availability of library resources and services
- Usage of library services.

Physical entry to the library's resources and grounds:

Table 1. Facilities surrounding the entrance to the library

Points on the checklist	University Libraries
Parking space	Yes
Signs or Symbols	Yes
Ramps with railings	Yes
Enough room for a wheelchair to enter between doors	Yes
Slides or ramps	Yes
Audio or Speech system	Yes

Table 1 Shows that Parking space, Signs or Symbols, Ramps with railings, Enough room for a wheelchair to enter between doors-, Slides or Ramps and Audio or speech system were provided by University Library.

Table 2. Space inside the library building

Checklist points	University Libraries
Shelves under reach	Yes
Tables of varying heights	Yes
Visible and audible fire alarm	Yes
Suitable Service desk	Yes

Table 2 Shows that Shelves under reach, Tables of varying heights, Visible and audible fire alarm and Suitable Service desk were provided by University Library.

Table 3. Washroom or toilet facilities

Points on the checklist	University Libraries
Signs indicating where the restroom or toilet is located	No
Roomy restrooms or wide doors	Yes
Visible and audible fire alarm	Yes
Mirrors and the wash basin should be at the right height	Yes

Table 3 Shows that Signs indicating where the restroom or toilet is located were not provide by University Library. Roomy restrooms or wide doors, Visible and audible fire alarm and Mirrors and the Wash Basin should be at the right height were provide by University Library.

Table 4. Facilities at circulation and reference desk

Points on the checklist	University Libraries
Suitable Desks	Yes
Suitable chairs to sit	Yes

Table 4 Shows that Suitable Desks and Suitable chairs to sit were provide by University Library.

Access to library materials:

Table 5. Facilities for users who are blind or visually impaired

Points on the checklist	University Libraries
Separately located section	Yes
Separately Reference Desk	Yes
Comfortable seating area	Yes
Audio visual special collection	Yes
Computers with adaptive technology	Yes

Table 5 Shows that Separately located section, Separate Reference Desk, Comfortable seating area, Audio visual special collection and Computers with adaptive technology were provide by University Library.

Availability of library resources and services

Table 6. Availability of library resources in usable formats

Points on the checklist	University Libraries
Magazines, newspapers, periodicals, and audiobooks	No
Books in Braille	Yes
DVD books or videos	Yes
Computer Support	Yes

Table 6 Shows that Magazines, Newspapers, Periodicals and audiobooks were not provide by University Library. Books in Braille, DVD books or videos and Computer Support were provided by University Library.

Table 7. Accessible information services for people with disabilities

Points on the checklist	University Libraries
Using sign language	No
Using the library's website	Yes
Email, SMS, and phone	Yes
Print Books	Yes
Subtitled video	Yes

Table 7 Shows that Using sign language were not provide by University Library. Using the library's website, Email/SMS and Phone, Print Books and Subtitle Video were provided by University Library.

Usage of library services:

Table 8. Special Services offered to persons with disabilities

Points on the checklist	University Libraries
Delivery service to your home	No

Dropbox functionality	Yes
Furniture that can be adjusted	Yes
Water for drinking is within reach	Yes

Table 8 Shows that Delivery services to your home were not provided by University Library. Dropbox functionality, Furniture that can be Adjustable and Water for drinking is within reach were provided by University Library.

Conclusions: Libraries are essential for enabling people with impairments to fully engage in society. Libraries should employ universal design-based solutions to make sure that their resources, policies, and services are inclusive of all users. There are some certain factors need to be considered at the planning stage. They are:

- Services should be added or developed in accordance with the needs of library patrons.
- The building and other infrastructure facilities can be established by adhering to standard rules and procedures.
- Awareness programs on regular basis.
- In-service training is needed for library professional

References:

1. Ai Squared. (2009). *ZoomText*. <http://www.aisquared.com/products> (accessed March 02, 2018)
2. Bandyopadhyay, R. (2008). Information literacy and public library services in West Bengal, India. pp. 129-136.
3. Cassner, M., Maxey-Harris, C., & Anaya, T. (2011). Differently able: a review of academic library websites for people with disabilities. *Behavioral & Social Sciences Librarian*, 30(1), 33-51.
4. Copeland, C. A. (2011). Library and information center accessibility: The differently-able patron's perspective. *Technical Services Quarterly*, 28(2), 223-241.
5. Erickson, W., C. Lee, and S. von Schrader. (2010). *Disability Statistics from the 2008 American Community Survey (ACS)*. Ithaca, N.Y.: Cornell University Rehabilitation Research and Training Center

on Disability Demographics and Statistics (Stats RRTC). [http://www. disabilitystatistics.org](http://www.disabilitystatistics.org) (accessed March 02, 2018).

6. Irvall, B., & Nielsen, G. S. (2005). *Access to libraries for persons with disabilities - Checklist* (No. IFLA Professional Reports, No. 89) (p. 18). The Hague: International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions.
7. Majumder, K. (2017). Community Information Services through Public Libraries and Information Centres: an experience in West Bengal, India. *Qualitative and Quantitative Methods in Libraries*, 5(4), 797-804.
8. Roy, P. C., & Bandyopadhyay, R. (2009). Designing barrier free services for visually challenged persons in the academic libraries in India.
9. Solanki, S.B., & Mandaliya, S. (2016). Enhancing library resources access for different abled person through ICT. *International Journal of Information Sciences and Techniques (IJIST)*, 6(1). (Accessed March 02, 2018).
10. Wijayaratne, A. (2011). Readiness in academic libraries to serve the differently-abled patrons.